

ANNEXURE 3.3: Figures

Figure A3.3.1: Merged physicochemical profile plots of the 401-nucleotides sequence at the ES position. The normalized parameter values are on the y-axis, while the nucleotide location relative to the ES (at 0) is on the x-axis. The highlighted grey region denotes the 50-length segment undergoing the physicochemical transition at these boundaries.

Figure A3.3.2: Merged physicochemical profile plots of the 401-nucleotides sequence at the EE position. The normalized parameter values are on the y-axis, while the nucleotide location relative to the EE (at 0) is on the x-axis. The highlighted grey region denotes the 50-length segment undergoing the physicochemical transition at these boundaries.

Figure A3.3.3: Profiles of the seven normalized structural and energetic parameters at the EI junctions in *Mus musculus*. (A) Exon-start, (B) Exon-end. Each line represents a major structural or energetic parameter. The four structural parameters were obtained by combining the individual parameters within that category. These parameters show the actual structural and energy change at the two boundaries.

Figure A3.3.4: Profiles of the seven normalized structural and energetic parameters at the EI junctions in *Caenorhabditis elegans*. (A) Exon-start, (B) Exon-end. Each line represents a major structural or energetic parameter. The four structural parameters were obtained by combining the individual parameters within that category. These parameters show the actual structural and energy change at the two boundaries.

Figure A3.3.5: Profiles of the seven normalized structural and energetic parameters at the EI junctions in *Plasmodium falciparum* (Protista). (A) Exon-start, (B) Exon-end. Each line represents a major structural or energetic parameter. The four structural parameters were obtained by combining the individual parameters within that category. These parameters show the actual structural and energy change at the two boundaries.

Figure A3.3.6: Profiles of the seven normalized structural and energetic parameters at the EI junctions in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (Fungi). (A) Exon-start, (B) Exon-end. Each line represents a major structural or energetic parameter. The four structural parameters were obtained by combining the individual parameters within that category. These parameters show the actual structural and energy change at the two boundaries.

Figure 3.3.7: Profiles of the seven normalized structural and energetic parameters at the EI junctions in *Arabidopsis thaliana* (Plantae). (A) Exon-start, (B) Exon-end. Each line represents a major structural or energetic parameter. The four structural parameters were obtained by combining the individual parameters within that category. These parameters show the actual structural and energy change at the two boundaries.